

Research Article

DoART: Autism Recreation Therapy Mobile Game Application

Mohd Iftitah Jamil^{1,*}, Alya Fathiah Afarizal², Amiera Maisara Shahabudin³, and Aziera Mohd Ishak⁴

¹ Graphic & Multimedia Department, Faculty of Creative Multimedia, KPTM Batu Pahat, 83300 Batu Pahat; iftitah@gapps.kptm.edu.my

² Graphic & Multimedia Department, Faculty of Creative Multimedia, KPTM Batu Pahat, 83300 Batu Pahat; bpj221410167@student.kptm.edu.my

³ Graphic & Multimedia Department, Faculty of Creative Multimedia, KPTM Batu Pahat, 83300 Batu Pahat; bpj221410168@student.kptm.edu.my

⁴ Graphic & Multimedia Department, Faculty of Creative Multimedia, KPTM Batu Pahat, 83300 Batu Pahat; bpj221410169@student.kptm.edu.my

* Correspondence: iftitah@gapps.kptm.edu.my; +60173926502.

Abstract: DoART or Autism Recreation Therapy is a visual art digital game application designed for autistic students to aid in their learning and recreation learning process. It addresses the difficulties these students face in traditional face-to-face learning and communication. Face to face and conversation technique used in current lesson for Autism students can be stressful. While doing the old teaching technique, Autism students having difficulty to follow the current module of visual art subject using book-based learning in school. This will result the poor outcome for their learning process. Visual art subject can be an important element in the educational process for autism students because this subject is able to highlight creativity and is also able to generate students psychomotor and cognitive processes. The approach of using digital game-based learning is able to increase the concentration of autism students in focusing on the visual art subject. In helping autistic students to focus more on learning process especially visual art subjects, DoART is produced by including interesting elements and filling games that are in line with the learning syllabus. This digital game-based learning application can be commercialized as the main material for autism student to learn the visual art subject. This game application is able to benefit not only autistic students, but it can also help parents and teachers to monitor the student's learning process more easily and flexibly. DoART is able to be commercialized to the autism community and it is able to provide opportunities for those involved like NASOM to take advantage of this application.

Keywords: Game based education, Autism, Visual art, Art therapy

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888334

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the *Modul Pendidikan Khas Bermasalah Pembelajaran* (2010) states that this group of children with special needs consists of children who have difficulty learning. Children with learning problems are described in this module as having various types of categories and one of them is autism spectrum disorder. The special education system that exists in the country at this time can to some extent help the autism children receive knowledge in a methodical manner according to their suitability. A Framework for Developing Culture-Based Multi-Modal Mind Games: Improving Social Interaction Skills of Autistic Children (2015) states that children with autism experience problems for eye-to-eye

social interaction, facial expressions, body posture and also communication problems. Autism is also called a neurodevelopmental disorder that is characterized by a lack of social communication and is also limited in an interest and often has repetitive behaviour (Holy Hodges et. al, 2020).

The problems in the process of social interaction by autism students can be clearly seen in the writings of Jeremy Sarachan (2012) who stated that autism have problems in the sensory system, problems with social behaviour, inflexibility, attention problems, problems in understanding the perspective of the surrounding community and also pragmatic difficulties. Muneeb Imtiaz Ahmad et.al (2011) explains that children with autism often face communication problems, emotional and social disorders. Muneeb Imtiaz Ahmad also explained that if it can be seen nowadays, games are not only seen to be directed towards elements that have interactive, engaging features and also as entertainment but it is seen more for its use either from education, learning and also as a material to help those in need.

1.1 Digital Game Based Learning

The use of digital game-based learning is very necessary in education process for autism students. S. Parsons et.al (2005) stated that autism students have a great affinity with technology such as computers. By using game in learning, it can avoid the communication process by autism students to the environment. The difficult learning process of autism students can be solved by applying game techniques in learning process because the game is able to provide role-playing scenarios and also a slow pace process at the same time allowing autism students to fully process the learning process (S. Loeppky, 2006).

Whyte, Smyth & Scherff (2015) found that autism is more able to succeed and are more motivated in academic learning when using games compared to normal learning techniques. Learning that uses games can further develop the creative thinking process. Madhya Zhagan et. al (2017) stated that digital games are very important in helping autism students to communicate. Aksoy (2005) stated that with the help of games as a tool in the learning process, it can simultaneously develop and improve students' creative thinking talent. Teachers and educators also need to play a role in the learning process by using game-based learning in teaching session. Tamara R. Meredith (2016) states that teachers and educators need to focus on using non-traditional approach methods such as the use of game-based learning.

1.2 Visual Art

Cox and Eames (1999) stated that autism group has good skills in the artistic field and is interested in the process of producing works of art. The importance of this art subject should be taken as an important element in helping autism students follow the learning process. Spivey (2008) stated that children with autism will use non-verbal communication in describing their feelings and this is illustrated through the process of producing art. Indirectly, the communication problems of these autism students in following the learning session can be reduced through the art process. The approach of using visual art subjects in the learning process of autism students is important. The subject of visual art is not only a normal process in learning, but it crosses the curriculum to become the basis for other subjects which involves the process of producing works to create interest, personality, creativity and sensitivity to the environment (Sharulnizam Ramli, Syed Abu Bakar & Sabzali Musa Khan, 2017).

Martin (2009) explain visual art is very important in the learning process of autism students because this group relies heavily on visual, concrete and hand on therapies. The emphasis on visual art as a subject that needs to be emphasized to autism students is because it is a good therapy in the learning process. Quadri & Oluwasegun (2014) in their writing stated that visual art is a very effective and versatile therapy for people with problems such as autism. It can provide the peace that autism

students need in the learning process and at the same time can have an impact on their academic development. Teachers can use visual art subjects to monitor non-verbal communication processes, emotional expressivity, social connectivity, intellectual acuity and content mastery (Amanda Newman-Godfrey & Lauren Stichter, 2017).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Looking at the problems with autistic students' learning processes, there are methods and processes that can assist these individuals. The use of digital game-based learning should be considered in light of the communication barriers and how autistic students interact during the learning process. Digital game-based learning is a promising educational approach that is consistent with current learning theories and has produced positive results across a wide range of domains. However, its successful implementation is dependent on game design, careful integration into the curriculum, and addressing practical issues. The learning process for autistic students can be made more engaging by integrating the actual visual arts learning syllabus into a mobile game application. This not only helps to produce high-quality learning materials but also serves as a therapy resource for autistic students.

3. FINDINGS

The product named DoART (Autism Recreation Therapy) is a digital game application in smart devices such as mobile phones and tablets. This game application will develop taking into account the content that focuses on visual art digital education-based games taught in schools. In specifying the product produced, it will go through the process of identifying the appropriate and necessary users to use it. If you look at the products produced, it is clear that they focus on autistic students, parents who have autistic children and also teachers in special schools. This digital game-based learning and application can be commercialized as the main material for autism student to learn the visual art subject.

4. DISCUSSION

This mobile game application idea was created to ensure that autism students can progress through the learning process in a more effective and quality manner. The digital game-based learning Technique allows autism students to learn visual arts in a more engaging way and serves as a form of therapy for them. The DoART application was created using the NABC model which is Need, Approach, Benefit, and Competitor. The game application will help those in need. Autism students are the ones who most needed by the DoART mobile application. Teachers and parents are also in need of this application. Government agencies, such as the Malaysian Ministry of Education, as well as non-governmental organizations, such as NASOM, are among those who require this application. All of those listed appear to be in need of an application that includes elements such as art classes, a fun learning process, and digital learning materials.

Approach focusses on how this application is developed. This mobile game application was created to emphasize the importance of digital game-based learning by incorporating a learning system into an application that uses the mobile game medium. This application will focus on visual arts education and will include a game-based curriculum. The DoART application aims to benefit users. This benefit refers to the financial savings that users will experience as a result of not having to purchase art material as well as reading materials such as books. Furthermore, it allows users to more easily monitor the learning process of autism students, whether at school or home. While for the Competitor part, competition from other application developers when creating this application is the main issue. This is because many well-known application developers have created applications aimed at autistic students. Nonetheless, this DoART application has the potential to be the best application to use because it using actual art syllabus in the classroom.

5. CONCLUSION

The use of DoART mobile game application is able to help teachers, parents and students in following the visual art learning process more easily, efficiently and creatively. Besides, in the learning process, what is more important is how students are able to understand everything presented by the teachers and also as therapy session. By the implement of DoART mobile game application in education process for ASD students, it can describe the fact that digital games are able to engage learners on an affective, behavioural, cognitive, and sociocultural level.

Acknowledgements: The authors would like to express gratitude and big thanks to Kolej Poly-Tech MARA Batu Pahat, the innovation unit and also research and publication unit of KPTMBP for the assistance and financial support that has been given in producing this innovation and publication.

References

- Amanda Newman-Godfrey & Lauren Sticher. (2017). *Visual Arts Curriculum for Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder*. Springer International Publishing.
- Aksoy, G. (2005). *Create a Button Science Education Scientific Method Process-based Learning Products, The Effect of UNMEE*. Zonguldak Karaelmas University.
- Cox, M. & Eames, K. (1999). *Contrasting Styles of Drawing in Gifted Individuals with Autism*. *Autism: The International Journal of Research and Practice*.
- Hodges H, Fealko C, Soares N. (2020). *Autism spectrum disorder: definition, epidemiology, causes, and clinical evaluation*. *Transl Pediatr*. S55-S65. doi: 10.21037/tp.2019.09.09. PMID: 32206584; PMCID: PMC7082249
- Jeremy Sarachan. (2012). *Virtual Floortime: Using Games to Engage Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder*. IEEE International Games Innovation Conference.
- Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia. (2010). *Modul Pendidikan Khas Bermasalah Pembelajaran: PKU3101 Pengenalan Kepada Pendidikan Khas*. Institut Pendidikan Guru, Kementarian Pelajaran Malaysia.
- Madhya Zhagan, Ooi Shi Ling & Seethalaxmi. (2017). *Computer-Assisted Technology (CAT) Strategy to Enhance Creative Art in Children With autism Spectrum Disorder*. *Jurnal Kurikulum & Pengajaran Asia Pasifik*.
- Martin, N. (2009). *Art Therapy and Autism: Overview and recommendations*. *Art Therapy: Journal of the American Art Therapy Association*, 26(4).
- Meredith, T. (2016). *Game-Based Learning in Professional Development for Practicing Educators: A Review of the Literature*. Tec Trends: Linking Research & Practice to Improve Learning.
- Muneeb Imtiaz Ahmad et al. (2011). *A Game-based Intervention for Improving the Communication Skills of Autistic Children in Pakistan*. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.
- Quadri, Oluwasegun Olawale. (2014). "Visual art Therapy: A Viable Tool for Children Diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder." *Proceedings of the 9th UNILAG Annual Research Conference and Fair*.
- Rafiza Mohd Hanifa et al. (2015). *A Framework for Developing Culture-Based Multi-Modal Mind Games: Improving Social Interaction Skills of Autistic Children*. *Jurnal Teknologi (Sciences & Engineering)* 75:3 (2015) 95–101. Penerbit UTM Press.
- Ramli, S., Bakar, S. A. S. A., & Khan, S. M. (2017). *Cabaran yang Dihadapi Pendidikan Seni Visual dengan Kemunculan Teknologi Maklumat dan Komunikasi (ICT) di Malaysia*. *Jurnal Pengajian Melayu*.
- S. Loeppky. (2006). *Gaming and Students with Asperger's Syndrome: A literature Review*.
- S. Parsons, P. Mitchell, A. Leonard. (2005). *Do Adolescents with Autistic Spectrum Disorders Adhere to Social Conventions in Virtual Environments?"* *Autism*, vol. 9, pp. 95-117.
- Spivey, B. L. (2008). *Using music and art with children with autism or other learning disabilities*. Super Duper Publications.
- Whyte, E., Smyth, J., & Scherff, K. (2015). *Designing Serious Game Interventions for Individuals with Autism*. *Journal of Autism & Developmental Disorders*, 45(12), 3820– 3831.